

Table 2. Resistance of rice cultivars (lines) to 7 pathogenic groups of BB in China 21 d after inoculation.

Variety (line)	Reaction ^a to pathogenic group							Origin	Use
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII		
Milyang 23	1	5	3	5	3	5	5	Korea	Hybridization
DV85	5	7	3	3	1	5	3	Bangladesh	Hybridization
IR54	3	3	3	3	5	3	3	IRRI	Hybridization
IRBB 7	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	IRRI	Resistance source
BR568-15-4-2-2-3	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	Bangladesh	Resistance source
C702015	1	3	3	3	3	3	5	Taiwan (China)	Resistance source
C722355	1	3	3	5	5	3	3	Taiwan (China)	Resistance source
Suwon	3391333351							Korea	Resistance source

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale 0-9.

regions of the northern part beyond the Yangtze River. *Xa-3*, *Xa-4*, *xa-5*, *Xa-6*, or *Xa-7* resistance sources are best in indica-japonica rice cropping regions along the

Yangtze River. *Xa-4*, *xa-5*, and *Xa-7* resistance sources are needed in indica rice cropping regions in the south China coastal area. □

Resistance to tungro in some wild relatives of rice

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We tested 16 accessions of wild rice *Oryza* spp. for antibiosis to green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. Distant, resistance to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) infection, and tolerance for tungro.

To test for antibiosis, a 10-d-old seedling of each accession was placed in a test tube with five GLH nymphs (2d instar), with 10 replications. Antibiosis of each accession was rated on a 1-5 scale by counting surviving GLH nymphs every day for 3 d. Those same seedlings (15-d-old) were inoculated with 10 viruliferous GLH adults/seedling for 4 h. Leaves were individually sampled 3 wk after inoculation, and tested for RTBV and RTSV by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. Disease severity of each accession was scored at 4 wk after

Reactions of wild species of rice to GLH and tungro disease.

Genome	Species	IRGC acc. no.	Origin	Anti-biosis to GLH ^a	Plants tested (no.)	Infected plants ^b (%)			Average severity ^c
						B+S	B	S	
AA	<i>O. nivara</i>	102463	Bangladesh	5	38	74	26	0	3
		102175	India	1	18	0	78	0	5
		105333	India	1	49	2	59	0	2
		105409	Sri Lanka	5	39	69	18	3	2
		105417	Sri Lanka	4	18	50	11	6	2
BB	<i>O. punctata</i>	105456	Sri Lanka	4	3	67	33	0	5
		103896	Tanzania	1	17	0	53	0	2
BBCC	<i>O. minuta</i>	105158	Kenya	2	49	0	37	0	3
		101126	Philippines	1	20	5	50	0	3
CC	<i>O. eichingeri</i>	101141	Philippines	1	36	0	56	0	5
		105414	Sri Lanka	2	47	47	43	0	5
CC	<i>O. officinalis</i>	105365	Thailand	1	27	0	0	0	2
		105394	China	3	32	9	81	0	3/7 ^d
CC	<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	105660	Sri Lanka	1	13	15	31	8	5
		105448	Sri Lanka		4	50	25	0	3
CCDD	<i>O. latifolia</i>	100914	Mexico	1	23	57	0	13	3
AA	<i>O. sativa</i> (check varieties)	ARC11554	India	1	54	2	39	0	3
		Utri Merah	Indonesia	5	54	2	52	0	3
		TN1	Taiwan	5	53	96	4	0	9
		IR22	Philippines	5	57	90	10	0	9

^aScale of 1 (resistant) to 5 (susceptible). ^bInfected with both RTBV and RTSV (B+S), with RTSV (S), or with RTBV (B). ^cScale 1 (no symptoms) to 9 (more than 50% plant height reduction and yellow to orange leaf discoloration), using Nasanuddin et al scale.

^dSegregating.

inoculation.

One accession of *O. officinalis* (105365) showed high antibiosis to GLH and resistance to both RTBV and RTSV infection (see table). Two accessions of *O. nivara* (102175, 105333), two of *O. punctata* (103896, 105158), and two of *O. minuta* (101126, 101141) showed high antibiosis to GLH and resistance to RTSV infection. Even with low antibiosis to GLH and severe infection with RTBV and RTSV, three accessions of *O. nivara* (102463, 105409, 105417) showed low scores for symptom severity, indicating tolerance for tungro.

These results suggest that a number of new sources of resistance to both RTBV and RTSV may be found among the wild rices. □

Distribution of rice varieties resistant to bacterial blight (BB) in Yunnan, China

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We screened 4,091 Yunnan rice varieties for resistance to BB caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* strain Jiangling 691: 6% were resistant, 84% were susceptible, and 10% were moderately resistant. The frequency of resistance differed within rice classifications (Table 1).

Resistance was more frequent among glutinous rices.

Table 2 shows more resistant varieties among japonica-irrigated-glutinous, japonica-irrigated-nonglutinous, and japonica-upland-glutinous rices. Mean

Table 1. Distribution of BB-resistant rices in Yunnan, China.

Classification	Varieties tested (no.)	Resistant varieties	
		no.	%
Indica	2186	83	3.8
Japonica	1905	159	8.4
Irrigated	3233	202	6.2
Upland	858	40	4.7
Nonglutinous	3183	159	5.0
Glutinous	908	83	9.1

resistance scales of these types are significantly lower than that of other types. In terms of average resistance, Yunnan rices could be classified into three significantly different resistance groups.

Presence of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in xylem cells of tungro-infected rice

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Earlier studies have shown that RTBV and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) are restricted to the phloem tissues of infected plants, and it has been suggested that only phloem feeding by green leafhopper (GLH) causes tungro infection. On GLH-resistant cultivars, however, it has been observed that GLH feeds mainly from the xylem and transmits primarily RTBV. We examined the location of RTBV in host cells in relation to tungro transmission.

Rice seedlings (15 d old) of tungro-susceptible cultivar TN1 and GLH-resistant cultivar ASD8 were inoculated with rice tungro viruses (RTVs) using adult GLHs. The leaf blades of infected plants were collected 30 d after inoculation for electron microscope study.

RTBV particles were found in xylem parenchyma cells as well as in phloem

Table 2. Distribution of resistant varieties in 8 classes and the significance level test of mean resistance scales.

Classification	Total (no.)	Resistant varieties		Mean resistance scale ^a
		no.	%	
Indica-irrigated-nonglutinous	1832	65	3.55	8.02 b
Indica-irrigated-glutinous	303	17	5.61	7.76 b
Indica-upland-nonglutinous	31	0	0	8.35 a
Indica-upland-glutinous	20	1	5.00	7.80 b
Japonica-irrigated-nonglutinous	679	70	10.31	7.38 c
Japonica-irrigated-glutinous	419	50	11.93	7.26 c
Japonica-upland-nonglutinous	641	24	3.74	7.96 b
Japonica-upland-glutinous	166	15	9.04	7.39 c
Total	4091	242	5.92	

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

cells of tungro-infected TN1 and ASD8 (see figure). RTSV was observed only in phloem cells and around the boundary between xylem and phloem tissues. In initial observations, RTBV in xylem cells were found in the third and fourth leaf position of infected plants.

These results suggest that GLH can transmit RTBV directly to xylem cells, where the virus multiplies and causes infection. They also support the observation that GLH feeds mainly from the xylem of GLH-resistant cultivars and transmits predominantly RTBV. □

RTBV in xylem parenchyma cells of rice cultivars TN1 (a) and ASD8 (b). R = ribosomes.

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Four upland rice varieties released in Sierra Leone

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The uplands account for about 70% of the rice area in Sierra Leone. In 1988, four new varieties (ROK17, ROK18, ROK19, ROK20), all foreign introductions, were released for upland planting (Table 1). These varieties surpassed check variety ROK16 in overall performance and farmer acceptability in field tests over four seasons.

Table 1. Mean performance of 4 newly released varieties in Sierra Leone.

Variety	Original name	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)
ROK17	LAC23	119	138	186	3.1
ROK18	IDSA-6	96	117	174	2.9
ROK19	FARROX 299	116	115	172	2.8
ROK20	IRAT161	103	118	178	3.0
ROK16	NGOVIE (local)	128	132	183	2.6

In varietal trials conducted for two seasons in farmers' fields in three villages in the North-Western Region, the new varieties consistently outyielded local check ROK16. Table 2 shows grain yields and some properties of the soils.

ROK17 is a local japonica selection from Liberia. It is a medium-duration cultivar, with bold grains much like ROK16. It is, however, more resistant to diseases and lodging than ROK16 and is suited to the high rainfall areas of East